

Compatibility of Nitrilotriacetic Acid and 3-Acetyl-4-Hydroxy-6-Methyl-2-Pyrone in the Coordination Sphere of Lanthanon Ions

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A study of the competition of 3-acetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-2-pyrone (dehydracetic acid, DHA) and nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) in the coordination sphere of lanthanon ions has been carried out by calculating reproporationation constant which relates the stability of the mixed ligand complex to those of the parent complexes formed by the same ligands. It has been found that NTA and DHA are incompatible ligands and mixed ligand complexes formed are less stable than either of the parent complexes. The fact is also supported by the observed change in free energy occurring during mixed ligand complex formation. All these studies have been carried out at $30.0 \pm 0.5^\circ$ and $\mu = 0.1$ (NaClO_4) in 50% v/v aqueous dioxane medium.

3-Acetyl-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-2-pyrone (DHA) has an α -pyrone structure and is a physiologically active compound. It has been used as fungistatic and fungicide, antibacterial agent, toxic and resistant to micro-organisms. 1 : 3 binary complexes of lanthanons with DHA and the mixed ligand complexes of these trivalent ions with DHA and NTA have been studied and the results reported in the present communication. The various metal ions investigated, required to calculate the reproporationation constant and the change in free energies which occurs during mixed ligand complex formation, are La(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III), Yb(III) and Y(III).

Experimental

DHA (Koch Light, England) solution was prepared in freshly distilled dioxane (E. Merck). NTA (Riedel) was dissolved in 3-equivalents of NaOH solution and was used as trisodium salt. All chemicals and solvents used were of A. R. quality and solutions were prepared in double distilled water. For ternary systems, the following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against a standard solution of tetramethylammonium hydroxide (TMAH) at $30.0 \pm 0.5^\circ$ and ionic concentration of $0.1 M \text{ NaClO}_4$, maintaining 50% (v/v) dioxane-water medium : (i) 5.0 ml perchloric acid (0.04 M), (ii) 5.0 ml perchloric acid (0.04 M) + 0.5 ml NTA (0.02 M), (iii) 5.0 ml perchloric acid (0.04 M) + 1.0 ml DHA (0.01 M), (iv) 5.0 ml perchloric acid (0.04 M) + 0.5 ml NTA (0.02 M) + 0.5 ml metal ion (0.02 M), (v) 5.0 ml perchloric acid (0.04 M) + 1.0 ml DHA (0.01 M) + 0.5 ml metal ion (0.02 M) and (vi) 5.0 ml perchloric acid (0.04 M) + 0.5 ml NTA (0.02 M) + 1.0 ml DHA (0.01 M) + 0.5 ml metal ion (0.02 M).

The binary systems were studied with 1 : 5 ratio of metal to ligand under identical conditions. For all calculations total volume was reduced from 20

ml to 19.7 ml due to contraction on mixing dioxane with water.

Results and Discussion

Formation constants : The formation constants of the binary complexes of lanthanons with DHA calculated by weighted least squares method of Sullivan *et al*¹ are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF THE METAL COMPLEXES WITH DHA CALCULATED BY WEIGHTED LEAST SQUARES METHOD AT $30.0 \pm 0.5^\circ$ AND $\mu = 0.1 M \text{ NaClO}_4$

Ln(III)	$\log \beta_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log K_3$	$\log \beta_3$	S_{min}
H ⁺	6.33	—	—	—	—	—
La	4.75	4.43	9.18	2.94	12.12	0.0468
Pr	4.88	4.55	9.43	3.15	12.58	0.0284
Nd	5.20	4.64	9.84	3.34	13.18	0.0188
Sm	5.44	4.74	10.18	3.49	13.67	0.0037
Gd	5.57	5.16	10.73	3.70	14.43	0.0092
Dy	5.81	5.30	11.11	4.14	15.25	0.0071
Yb	6.30	5.40	11.70	4.91	16.61	0.0580
Y	5.87	5.37	11.24	4.22	15.46	0.0477

In case of ternary systems, it was observed that NTA reacts with lanthanons at lower pH range as found from titration curves of (ii) and (iv) solutions. The titration curves of (iii) and (vi) solutions overlap in the lower pH range whereas at high pH there is divergence of the curves indicating the coordination of DHA with the species [Ln-NTA]. Also, the [Ln-NTA] species have much higher formation constants as compared to lanthanon-DHA complex and hence ligand exchange possibility is eliminated.

The overall reaction may thus be represented as

where K_{MAL} is the formation constant of the mixed species and is given by equation

$$K_{MAL} = \beta_{1,1} = \frac{[\text{Ln-NTA-DHA}]}{[\text{Ln-NTA}][\text{DHA}]}$$

$S_{m \pm n}$ values having the same significance as χ^2 with k degrees of freedom² have also been calculated for all systems.

Reproportionation constants: The stability of the mixed ligand complexes formed is related to the stability of the parent complexes formed by same ligands through reproportionation constant. This correlation is given by the following expression :

$$\beta_{i,j} = K_{\bar{a}} \beta_{m,0}^{i/m} \beta_{0,m}^{j/m}, [i+j=m]$$

Where $K_{\bar{a}}$ is reproportionation constant (Table 2). This constant is a measure of the compatibility of the various ligands in the coordination sphere of a given metal ion.

TABLE 2—FORMATION AND REPROPORTIONATION CONSTANTS AND $S_{m \pm n}$ VALUES OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES AT $30.0 \pm 0.5^\circ$ AND $\mu = 0.1 M$ NaClO₄.

Ln(III)	$\log \beta_{m,0}^{i/m}$ (M-NTA)	$\log \beta_{0,m}^{j/m}$ (M-DHA)	$\log \beta_{i,j}$ (M-NTA-DHA)	$K_{\bar{a}}$	$S_{m \pm n}$
La	17.65	9.18	13.35	0.871	0.0140
Pr	19.90	9.43	14.09	0.794	0.0465
Nd	19.36	9.84	14.57	0.933	0.0528
Sm	20.51	10.18	15.07	0.537	0.0952
Gd	20.79	10.73	15.67	0.813	0.1596
Dy	21.16	11.11	15.90	0.589	0.0870
Yb	21.73	11.70	16.63	0.832	0.1631
Y	21.73	11.24	15.64	0.144	0.0425

* Values redetermined under present set of conditions⁷.

Formational energies: The individual bond strengths M-A and M-L in the complex MA_iL_j can be calculated from the formation constant of the mixed ligand complex and the parent complexes MA_j and ML_i using the following equations :

$$F_A = \frac{RT}{4j} \ln \beta_{i,j} \frac{\beta_{j,0}}{\beta_{0,i}}$$

$$F_L = \frac{RT}{4} \ln \beta_{i,j} \frac{\beta_{0,i}}{\beta_{j,0}}$$

The bond strengths in the parent complexes MA_m and ML_m are calculated from the equations :

$$F'_A = \frac{RT}{2m} \ln \beta_{m,0}$$

$$F'_L = \frac{RT}{2m} \ln \beta_{0,m}$$

The differences in free energies calculated from these equations characterise the changes of M-A and M-L bond energies which occur during mixed ligand complex formation. The results of the present investigations are listed in Table 3.

Discussion

Pure statistical consideration predicts $\beta_{0,1}/\beta_{0,2}$ values as 3.27 and 4.92, respectively for a ligand

TABLE 3—FORMATIONAL ENERGIES OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES IN CALS/MOLE

Ln(III)	M-NTA (parent)	M-NTA (mixed)	Change in free energy	M-DHA (parent)	M-DHA (mixed)	Change in free energy
La	6115	6624	509	3182	2631	-551
Pr	6549	6950	401	3303	2818	-485
Nd	6708	7199	491	3411	2901	-510
Sm	7113	7452	339	3529	2995	-534
Gd	7210	7654	444	3719	3210	-541
Dy	7335	7712	377	3851	3310	-628
Yb	7532	8101	569	4056	3428	-558
Y	7532	7504	-28	3896	3338	

functioning as bidentate or tridentate in the presence of lanthanon ions⁸. Our results indicate that $\beta_{0,1}$ values are larger than $\beta_{0,2}$ values and their ratio is less than 3.27 in all the cases, suggesting the bidentate nature of DHA.

It may be noted from Table 1 that the value of formation constants for binary complexes increases regularly from lanthanum to ytterbium and no gadolinium break has been observed. Also, the value for yttrium complex is found to be quite close to the value of dysprosium. Depending upon the nature of the ligand, the formation constant values of yttrium complexes are at times close to those of dysprosium complexes and at others close to praseodymium. Because of its size, yttrium should be found near holmium except when lack of ligand field stabilization moves it closer to gadolinium. Probably polarizability effects or/and minor but variable contributions of covalent bonding are responsible for the erratic behaviour of yttrium⁴.

Results of the present investigations show that mixed ligand complexes formed are less stable than either of the parent complexes (Tables 2 and 3). M-NTA bond strengths increase while M-DHA bond strengths decrease. The lower stability of the mixed ligand complexes can be explained on the basis of electrostatic considerations. The driving force for the binding of secondary ligand L^- with $[MA]$ should be less than that for the binding of L^- with $[M(aq)]^{a+}$. Further, NTA molecule with a bigger size is expected to produce a greater steric hindrance to the entry of the second ligand in the coordination sphere of the metal ion and decreases the stability to a great extent.

The lower stability of the mixed ligand complexes is also due to incompatible nature of NTA and DHA in the coordination sphere of lanthanon ions and is reflected in the values of reproportionation constant which is less than unity in all the cases. It has been observed that if the geometrical structures and bond types of the parent complexes differ from each other, the ligands are incompatible and the mixed ligand complexes formed are less stable than either of the parent complexes⁹. In such cases, the bonds between the metal ion and one of the ligands become more ionic and the bonds between the metal ion and the second ligand become

more covalent. These effects are of opposite sign and the net energy change may be positive or negative depending upon the nature of ligands and metal ion involved in complex formation⁶.

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